

The Effect of Sense of Meaningfulness and Job Satisfaction on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and its Implications on The Performance of Members At Kodam Iskandar Muda Aceh

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Abstract: This study aims to test the sense of meaningfulness and job satisfaction role in organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and its implications for member performance at the Aceh Iskandar Muda Military Area Command (Kodam IM). The population was all members of the Kodam IM, which was 144 members, so the method used was the census because the population was relatively small. Data were analyzed using the AMOS SEM statistical equipment. The result proves that the Meaningfulness, OCB, and Kodam IM member performance are good; Meaningfulness influences the OCB members of the Kodam IM; Satisfaction influences OCB members of the Kodam IM; Meaningfulness influences Kodam IM member performance; Satisfaction influences Kodam IM member performance; OCB influences Kodam IM member performance; Meaningfulness influences member performance through OCB members of the Kodam IM; and Satisfaction influences member performance through OCB members of Kodam IM. These findings explain that the model of increasing the member performance of Kodam IM is a function of increasing Meaningfulness, satisfaction, and OCB in its members.

Keywords: Sense of Meaningfulness, job satisfaction, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Member Performance

I. Introduction

The Aceh Iskandar Muda Military Area Command (Kodam IM) is the Defense Command for the Province of Aceh. Human resources are the main asset for military organizations. Following the main tasks of the Kodam IM, it is certainly necessary to have competence from each member so that they can carry out their duties as well as possible and be able to provide security to the people in Aceh Province in particular. According to (Dwingspana, Sumari, & Prihantoro, 2016) in his research, it was stated that Kodam IM member performance had decreased as shown by indications namely absenteeism without permission (IHTI), desertion violations, and returning to work prematurely, and members' work expectations had not been maximized. The phenomenon related to Kodam IM member performance is one of the topics that the Commander of the Kodam IM constantly discusses. This is reflected in the Leadership Meeting (Rapim) activities held by the Kodam IM on 18 February 2019 at Balai Teuku Umar (BTU) Makodam IM.

Many factors affect member performance in the Kodam IM, one of which is organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). OCB is extra behavior that is not part of the formal obligations of a member but serves to support the organization effectively. OCB at the Kodam IM has not shown maximum enthusiasm. In the pre-survey, several respondents found an increase in extra roles inside and outside of their work so that they could work more effectively in achieving organizational goals, but this still could not be realized because there were still some members who carried out actions that did not comply with the rules/low motivation, ignoring responsibility, and trying to work optimally.

Other factors that also influence the decrease or increase in member performance other than OCB members of the Kodam IM, there is also a sense of meaningfulness for members in carrying out their duties and functions as members of the Kodam IM, especially in improving their performance, so that the sense of meaningfulness of members becomes something important so that can have an impact on improving member performance. With a sense of the meaningfulness

of members in an organization, these members feel that they are an integral part of an organization because members feel they have an important role or the member concerned becomes involved in creating individual performance.

Kodam IM wants the highest possible level of work performance for its members. This is of course balanced by providing satisfaction to all its members, namely meeting the needs and expectations of its members. However, in reality, the members of the Kodam IM do not seem to feel satisfied at work. Some of the causes include being bored at working with the same job and wanting to find new experiences and work rewards. Dissatisfaction and low levels of member satisfaction can cause disturbances and obstacles as well as disruptions to an organization as well as all processes within it. This is marked by absences without permission (THTI), violations of desertion, and leaving work prematurely, as well as members' work expectations that have not been maximized.

II. Literature

Member Performance

Every member of the organization is required to make a positive contribution through good performance, considering that organizational performance depends on the performance of its members (Gibson, Ivancevic, & Konopaske, 2012). Performance is an organizational behavior that is directly related to the production of goods or the delivery of services (Admin_prokomsetda, 2019). (Yukl, 2010) and (Gibson et al., 2012) define performance as the result of work related to organizational goals such as quality, efficiency, and other effectiveness criteria. (Prawirosentono, 2010) and (Edison, Riyanti, & Yustiana, 2016) states that performance is the result of a process that refers to and is measured over a certain period based on predetermined provisions or agreements to achieve the goals of an organization. (Idowu, 2017) and (A. S. Munandar, 2001) state the performance appraisal system is quite effective in offering a comprehensive analysis of employee performance. Based on these opinions, it can be concluded that member performance is the ability of a member or group of people to complete the tasks assigned to them following predetermined criteria effectively without any violation of statutory regulations.

OCB

OCB was introduced by Organ in the early 1980s, but well before that year (Barnard, 1938) used a concept similar to OCB and called it a willingness to cooperate (willingness to cooperate). According to (Aldag & Reschke, 1997) OCB is the contribution of individuals in exceeding the demands of roles in the workplace. Meanwhile (Organ, 2015) mentions that OCB is independent individual behavior, not related directly or explicitly to the reward system, and can improve the effective functioning of the organization. (Huang, Wang, & Xie, 2014) states, OCB behavior is a term used to identify employee behavior. Such behavior is defined "as behavior that benefits the organization or intends to benefit the organization that directly leads to role expectations. OCB behavior can be done anywhere, you don't have to wait in a large organization or company (Putri, 2018). OCB behavior is a form of behavior that is an individual choice and initiative, not related to the organization's formal reward system but in aggregate increases organizational effectiveness (Hendrawan, Suchayawati, & Indriyani, 2017).

Sense of Meaningfulness

Sense of Meaningfulness is a new paradigm in human resource management. (Herminingsih, 2012) mentioning the dimensions of spirituality that have the highest average values are altruism and courtesy, but those that have the highest loading factor are grace and a sense of meaningfulness. (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002) postulates that everyone has a "craving for meaning," an innate drive to ascribe meaning to his life. Failing to find meaning in life can result in an "existential emptiness," a state of emptiness and aimlessness. Sense of Meaningfulness arises first from individual feelings that are internalized and live in their experiences while working (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Meaningfulness in work can encourage employees to play an extra role in developing the organization (Nasurdin, Nejati, & Mei, 2013). Work can be meaningful if the individual feels the work being done is fun, gives a sense of challenge as desired, and both require strength from others (Steger & Dik, 2009). The meaning of work is the most important psychological resource to prevent negative results given by a member or employee (Humphrey, Nahrgang, & Morgeson, 2007); (Steger, 2012). This study will often mention the sense of meaningfulness as "meaningfulness" only.

Job Satisfaction

(Locke, 1976) and (Robbins & Judge, 2014) mention when people talk about employee attitudes, what is meant is job satisfaction which describes a member's positive feelings towards his work. (Judge & Mueller, 2012) define job satisfaction as an assessment that expresses satisfaction and positive feelings towards one's work. (Mathis, 2006) mentions the basic notion of job satisfaction is a state with positive emotions resulting from evaluating the work experience of members. There are several theories regarding job satisfaction that are most well-known, including the

interpersonal comparison theory, the theory of justice, and the two-factor theory. The researcher chose to use one of the three theories, namely the two-factor theory from Frederick Herzberg or what is commonly called the motivator-hygiene theory. Motivator factors are situations that are desired by each member, including a pleasant work situation, work that is very interesting and full of challenges for members, getting opportunities to excel, and getting opportunities to get an appreciation for their work. While the hygiene factor is a situation that is very unwanted by members, such as wages or salaries that are not following work, there are relationship problems between co-workers, unpleasant working conditions, and not getting full responsibility for work. This study will often mention job satisfaction as "satisfaction" only.

Thinking Framework and Hypotheses

The study framework and hypotheses formed are described below

Figure 1. Thinking Framework

- Ha1 :Meaningfulness, OCB, and Kodam IM member performance are good.
- Ha2 :Meaningfulness affects the OCB members of the Kodam IM.
- Ha3 :Satisfaction affects the OCB of Kodam IM members.
- Ha4 :Meaningfulness affects Kodam IM member performance.
- Ha5 :Satisfaction affects Kodam IM member performance.
- Ha6 : OCB affects Kodam IM member performance.
- Ha7 :Meaningfulness affects member performance through OCB members of the Kodam IM.
- Ha8 :Satisfaction affects member performance through the OCB members of the Kodam IM.

III. Method

This study was conducted at the Aceh Iskandar Muda Military Area Command (Kodam IM). The objects of this research were meaningfulness, satisfaction, OCB, and the member performance of the Kodam IM. The population was all members of the Kodam IM, totaling 144 members, so the method used was the census because the population was relatively small.

This research collected data through the distribution of questionnaires, namely digging up information related to the variables studied. In the questionnaire, the Likert scale was provided according to the answer. Data were analyzed using the AMOS SEM statistical tool.

IV. Result

Descriptive Hypothesis

This testing of H1 was to see the variable conditions, the results are shown below.

Table 1. Respondent Perception

No	Variable	Average	Cut off	Information
1	Performance (Z)	3.58	3.41	Good
2	OCB(Y)	3.97		Good
3	Meaningfulness (X1)	3.68		Good
4	Satisfaction (X2)	3.78		Good

Source: Processed data (2022)

The table above shows the respondent perceptions for all variables that have obtained an average > 3.41. The next test is the test using a one-sample T-test with a significant ($\alpha = 5\%$) and a cut-off 3.41. The following table shows the result.

Table 2. H1 test

	Test Value = 3.41					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Meaningfulness	53.359	143	.000	18.34694	17.6673	19.0266
Satisfaction	55.042	143	.000	16.44417	15.8536	17.0347
OCB	51.305	143	.000	29.68722	28.5434	30.8310
Performance	57.797	143	.000	19.29833	18.6383	19.9583

Source: Processed Data (2022)

The results provide a value = 3.41. Table 2 above shows all variables have a sig (2-tailed) $0.000 < 0.05$. From these results, it can be seen that the member performance variables, OCB, meaningfulness, and satisfaction have been going well at the Kodam IM. This concludes the H1 is descriptively accepted.

Direct Effect

After fulfilling all the assumptions of the SEM modeling following the predetermined requirements, then the next step was to test the direct effect hypothesis using SEM. The test was based on the Critical Ratio (CR) and Probability (P) values, with the requirement of $CR > 1.96$; $P < 0.05$. The results of data processing are figured below.

Figure 2. Model Test

In the model figure above, the direct effect hypothesis testing is obtained as presented in the following table:

Table 3. Regression

Endogenous	exogenous	Standardize	S.E.	C.R.	P
OCB	<--- Sense_of_Meaningfulness	.271	.045	2.245	.013
OCB	<--- Satisfaction	.805	.090	8.828	***
Performance	<--- Sense_of_Meaningfulness	.357	.094	2.877	.001
Performance	<--- Satisfaction	.218	.109	2.099	.021
Performance	<--- OCB	.332	.116	3.009	.003

Source: Processed data (2022)

The table above can explain the direct effect between exogenous and endogenous variables, namely between the meaningfulness and satisfaction factors with OCB members at the Kodam IM. The test result above proves that the results of hypotheses 2 and 3 are accepted where:

- H₂: meaningfulness affects the OCB Members of the Kodam IM.
 H₃: Satisfaction affects OCB Members at the Kodam IM

The output of the model also explains the direct effect between the meaningfulness and satisfaction factors on member performance at the Kodam IM. The test result above proves that hypotheses 4 and 5 are accepted, where:

- H₄: meaningfulness affects member performance in the Kodam IM.
 H₅: satisfaction affects member performance in the Kodam IM

Furthermore, the output of the structural equation model also explains the OCB contribution to Kodam IM member performance. The test results prove that hypothesis 6 is accepted where :

- H₆: OCB affects the performance of Kodam IM members.

Indirect Effect

Meaningfulness on Kodam IM member performance through OCB

Testing H7 namely the meaningfulness contribution to Kodam IM member performance through OCB are as follows.

Figure 3. H7 Test

Testing H7 used the Sobel calculator is shown in the picture above. It provides the t-statistic $2.59 > 1.96$; $P < 0.01$. These results prove that H 7 is accepted where:

- H₇: OCB mediates the meaningfulness contribution to member performance at the Kodam IM

Satisfaction on Kodam IM member performance through OCB

Testing H8 namely the satisfaction contribution to member performance at the Kodam IM through OCB is shown in Figure below

Figure 4. H8 Test

Testing H8 used the Sobel calculator as shown in the picture above. It produces the t-statistic $2.72 > 1.96$; $P < 0.01$. This proves H8 is accepted, where:

H₈: OCB mediates the satisfaction contribution to member performance at the Kodam IM

Decision

Meaningfulness on OCB

From the results of testing hypothesis 2 as previously described, it can be seen that $CR > 1.96$; $P < 0.05$. This proves H2 is accepted. This reveals OCB is positively and significantly influenced by a sense of meaningfulness. This result is in line with (Khaidir, Yunus, & Idris, 2020); (Lam, Wan, & Roussin, 2015) where their findings also prove that one of the factors that influence OCB is a sense of meaningfulness.

In this research, the meaningfulness role size in influencing OCB members in the IM Military Command is 0.271. This means that by increasing the sense of meaningfulness felt by members of the IM Military Command, they will be able to increase their citizenship behavior by 27.1%. To increase OCB, members' sense of meaningfulness must be increased through their involvement in matters that are following their work interests. A sense of meaningfulness can be interpreted as a valuable goal or work goal, assessed concerning individual ideals or standards (Hackman & Oldham, 1980) in (Sudaryo & Sjarif, 2017). Lack of meaning in one's work can lead to alienation or 'detachment' from one's work (Montani, Boudrias, & Pigeon, 2017). The higher the level of alienation of a person in an organization, it is certain that it will be directly proportional to the decrease in their performance at work.

The field observations reveal it is very important to increase OCB members through a sense of meaningfulness. One very important thing that can be done to increase a sense of meaningfulness is to always involve all members in efforts to solve problems faced, make decisions, and respect all efforts or opinions expressed by members. These things will certainly be able to increase the member's sense of meaningfulness towards the IM Military Command. The higher the sense of meaningfulness possessed by members will increase the citizenship behavior of these members (Khaidir et al., 2020).

Satisfaction on OCB

H3 model test, namely the satisfaction contribution to OCB members of the Kodam IM, provides $CR > 1.96$; $P < 0.000 < 0.05$. This reveals H3 is accepted. These results can be interpreted that OCB is strongly influenced by the member satisfaction of the Kodam IM. This result is in line with (Fadhli, Lubis, Salmi, & Idris, 2020); (Varihana, Harmen, & Nizam, 2020); (Kurniawan, Mukhlis, & Musnadi, 2020); (Ritonga, Ibrahim, & Bahri, 2019); (Aprizka, Nasir, & Syafruddin, 2020); (Ikhsan, Adam, & Faisal, 2019) where they also prove that OCB has a very large impact on satisfaction. The satisfaction role size in influencing OCB is 0.805. This means an increase in the satisfaction of members at the Kodam IM by 100%, they will be able to increase OCB by 80.5%.

The field observations reveal to improve OCB through satisfaction, the leadership needs to improve and maintain the relationship between fellow members and also the relationship between members and leaders. In addition, the leadership must be able to increase the sense of security and comfort for all their members. In addition, each member must also increase mutual respect among others and all members must be able to overcome their feeling of boredom. Regarding the feeling of boredom among members, the leadership must provide equal opportunities for all members to be able to take time off from work so that each member can refresh to eliminate feelings of boredom at work.

Meaningfulness on Member Performance at the Kodam IM

Based on the H4 test, namely the meaningfulness contribution to Kodam IM member performance, $C.R > 1.96$; $P < 0.001 < 0.05$ were obtained. This proves H4 is accepted. These results indicate that Kodam IM member performance is affected by meaningfulness. This result is also supported by (Khaidir et al., 2020).

The size of the role of meaningfulness in influencing member performance at the Kodam IM is 0.357 or 35.7%, which means that with increasing meaningfulness felt by members at the Kodam IM, they will be able to increase their performance by 35.7%. Meaningfulness is a basic value that must be possessed by all members of the Kodam IM. So that with high meaningfulness will be able to improve their overall performance. With a high sense of significance, this will foster a sense of belonging, so with this sense, all members will devote all their efforts to improve their performance so that the goals of the organization can be achieved.

Satisfaction on Member Performance at the Kodam IM

Testing H5, namely the satisfaction contribution to member performance in the Kodam IM, produces $C.R > 1.96$; $P < 0.21 < 0.05$. This explains H5 is accepted. This describes the member performance of Kodam IM members is influenced by members' satisfaction. This result is also supported by (Andika, Adam, Djalil, & Nurdin, 2020); (Susanto,

Faisal, & Putra, 2019); (Muhammad, Musnadi, & Darsono, 2018); (A. Munandar, Musnadi, & Sulaiman, 2019); (Samsuar, Azis, & Faisal, 2019); (Akbar, Musnadi, & Putra, 2020); (Mukhlis, Musnadi, & Ridwan, 2020); (Fajrian, Musnadi, & Nadirsyah, 2020).

The size of the role of satisfaction in influencing member performance in the Kodam IM is 0.218. This value can be interpreted that by increasing the member's satisfaction by 100%, it will be able to increase member performance in the Kodam IM by 21.8%. Satisfaction is a general attitude towards one's work as the difference between the rewards received and the rewards believed to be received (DeCenzo, Robbins, & Verhulst, 2018). Satisfaction reflects one's feelings when getting what is wanted from what is expected. In terms of work, people who are satisfied with their jobs tend to display more developed jobs than before (Irwan, Musnadi, & Putra, 2021).

From The field observations it was found that to increase the satisfaction of members at the Kodam IM so that they will be able to improve their performance, the leadership at the Kodam IM must be able to increase the sense of security and comfort for all its members in carrying out their daily duties as state apparatus. Leaders must also improve the atmosphere of good working relations among fellow members and also with the leadership. Leaders must increase the application of the values of mutual respect among fellow members.

OCB on Member Performance at the Kodam IM

The H6 Test, namely the OCB contribution to member performance in the Kodam IM, obtains $CR\ 3.009 > 1.96$; $P\ 0.003 < 0.05$. These values prove H6 is accepted. This proves the member performance in the Kodam IM is influenced by OCB. This result is in line with (Samsuar et al., 2019); (Khaidir et al., 2020); (Jannati, Lubis, & Putra, 2022).

The OCB role size in influencing member performance in the Kodam IM is 0.332 or 33.2%. This means that with increasing OCB members at the Kodam IM, member performance at the Kodam IM will be increased by 33.2%. OCB represents the fact that this behavior has a certain impact on organizational effectiveness by adding a social framework to the workplace.

From the respondents' perceptions data, it was found that to improve OCB, it is mandatory for all members of the Kodam IM to always comply with the rules even if they are not supervised, each member is aware of always behaving honestly at work, always willing to help each other in solving difficult problems faced by fellow members, each member plays an active role in improving the performance, and reminds each other to avoid and prevent problems from arising.

Meaningfulness on Member Performance at the Kodam IM through OCB

Testing H7 used the Sobel calculator, providing the t-statistic $2.58 > 1.96$; $P\ 0.01$. The acquisition of this value proves that OCB partially mediates the role of meaningfulness in member performance at the Kodam IM. This proves H7 is accepted. The results of calculating the significance for path C' in the model of meaningfulness contribution to member performance at the Kodam IM through OCB as shown in the chart the following

Figure 5. Hypothesis 7 Mediation Chart

The picture above explains that the meaningfulness variable for OCB has a coefficient A with $\beta\ 0.271$; $P\ 0.013 < 0.05$. The coefficient B (OCB on member performance) has a $\beta\ 0.332$; $P\ 0.003 < 0.05$. The coefficient C (meaningfulness on member performance at the Kodam IM) has a $\beta\ 0.357$; $P\ 0.001 < 0.05$. The path coefficient C' (the meaningfulness on member performance at the Kodam IM through OCB) has a $\beta\ 0.271 \times 0.332 = 0.089$; $P\ 0.01 < 0.05$.

So testing H7 concludes the OCB partially mediates the role of meaningfulness in member performance in the Kodam IM. Partial mediation explains both directly and through OCB, the meaningfulness affects member performance at the Kodam IM. The OCB role size in the meaningfulness on member performance at the Kodam IM is 0.089 or 8.9%, which means that by increasing the OCB of members, it will be able to increase the meaningfulness contribution to member performance of the Kodam IM by 8.9%.

Satisfaction on Member Performance at the Kodam IM Through OCB

Testing H8 used the Sobel calculator, providing the t-statistic $2.72 > 1.96$; $P < 0.01$. The acquisition of this value proves that OCB partially mediates the role of satisfaction in member performance at the Kodam IM. This proves that testing hypothesis 8 is accepted. The results of calculating the significance for path C' in the model of satisfaction on member performance in the Kodam IM through OCB are shown in the following chart

Figure 6. Hypothesis 8 Mediation Chart

Based on the picture above, it can be explained that the variable satisfaction with OCB has a coefficient A with a β 0.805; $P < 0.000 < 0.05$. The coefficient B (OCB on member performance) has a β 0.332; $P < 0.003 < 0.05$. The coefficient C (satisfaction on member performance in the Kodam IM) has a β 0.218; $P < 0.021 < 0.05$. The path coefficient C' (meaningfulness on member performance at the Kodam IM through OCB) has a β $0.271 \times 0.332 = 0.267$; $P < 0.01 < 0.05$.

The result of testing H8 reveals OCB partially mediates the satisfaction contribution to member performance in the Kodam IM. Partial mediation means both directly and through OCB, satisfaction affects member performance in the Kodam IM. The OCB role size in the satisfaction contribution to member performance in the Kodam IM is 0.267 or 26.7%, which means that with increasing OCB members, it will be able to increase the satisfaction contribution to member performance in the Kodam IM by 26.7%.

V. Conclusion

The results conclude that:

1. The H1 descriptive testing shows that the meaningfulness, satisfaction, OCB, and member performance have gone well because all the average values of all variables > 3.41 and the sig 2 tailed < 0.05 .
2. The results of testing hypotheses 2 and 3 are accepted where OCB is positively and significantly influenced by meaningfulness and satisfaction. This can be seen from the acquisition of $CR > 1.96$; $P < 0.05$. Meaningfulness has a role of 27.1% in influencing OCB and satisfaction has a role of 80.5% in influencing OCB.
3. The results of testing hypotheses 4, 5, and 6 are accepted where Kodam IM member performance is influenced by meaningfulness, satisfaction, and OCB. It can also be seen from the acquisition of a $C.R > 1.96$ and the acquisition of a $P < 0.05$. The magnitude of the meaningfulness role in influencing member performance is 35.7%. The magnitude of satisfaction role in influencing member performance is 21.8% and the magnitude of OCB in influencing member performance is 33.2%.
4. Both hypotheses 7 and 8 are accepted where OCB partially mediates the role of meaningfulness and satisfaction with member performance in the Kodam IM. This is proven by the t statistics > 1.96 ; $P < 0.05$. The OCB role size in mediating the meaningfulness contribution to member performance is equal to 8.9% and the OCB role size in mediating the satisfaction contribution to member performance is equal to 26.7%.

These findings explain that the model of improving the performance of Kodam IM members is a function of increasing the Meaningfulness, satisfaction, and OCB of its members. The model that has been tested also validates several previous models, so academically this model has been supported by previous findings, and can be used as a basis for further research in the future by adding other variables to the model. Practically, this model can be a reference for policymakers on the research subject, namely the Kodam IM to further improve the performance of its members.

References

- [1.] Admin_prokomsetda. (2019). Teori Kinerja Anggota. Retrieved January 25, 2020, from bulelengkab.go.id website: <https://www.bulelengkab.go.id/detail/artikel/teori-kinerja-anggota-15>
- [2.] Akbar, R., Musnadi, S., & Putra, T. R. I. (2020). The Effect of Organizational Commitment, Emotional Intelligence, and Compensation on Performance of Satpol PP and WH Aceh Employee Through Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 3(3), 8–22.

- [3.] Aldag, R., & Reschke, W. (1997). *Employee value added: Measuring discretionary effort and its value to the organization*. USA: Madison School of Business.
- [4.] Andika, D., Adam, M., Djalil, M. A., & Nurdin, R. (2020). The Effect of Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance through Work Motivation (Case Study at Tax Service Office, Pratama Banda Aceh, Indonesia). *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 3(2), 164-168. <https://doi.org/10.36349/EASJEBM.2020.v03i02.22>
- [5.] Aprizka, K., Nasir, & Syafruddin. (2020). The Effect of Employee Empowerment and Self-efficacy on Job Satisfaction and Its Impact on Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Study in PT. PLN (Persero) Banda Aceh. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 3(3), 288-303.
- [6.] Barnard, C. I. (1938). *The Functions of the Executive*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- [7.] DeCenzo, D. A., Robbins, S. P., & Verhulst, S. L. (2018). *Fundamentals of Human Resource Management* (13th Ed.). New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [8.] Dwinguspana, E., Sumari, A. D. W., & Prihantoro, M. (2016). The Effect of Compensation on Discipline and Performance of Soldiers of the 11th Cavalry Battalion/Seserbu Kodam Iskandar Muda. *Jurnal Pertahanan*, 6(1), 169-191.
- [9.] Edison, E., Riyanti, A., & Yustiana, D. (2016). Organizational Culture in Employee Performance Improvement Aspect (Case Study at Perdana Wisata Hotel, Bandung). *Tourism Scientific Journal*, 1(2), 134-151. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.32659/tsj.v1i2.8>
- [10.] Fadhli, Z., Lubis, A. R., Salmi, M. A., & Idris, S. (2020). Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment and Its Impact on Employee Performance (A Case Study of Work Unit of Aceh Jaya District , Aceh Province , Indonesia). *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 4464(2), 159-163. <https://doi.org/10.36349/easjebm.2020.v03i02.008>
- [11.] Fajrian, A., Musnadi, S., & Nadirsyah. (2020). The Effect Of Competence, Professionalism And Work Environment On Job Satisfaction And Its Impact On Internal Auditor Performance Of PT Bank Negara Indonesia. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 3(4), 126-142. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.35409/IJBMER.2020.3190>
- [12.] Gibson, J., Ivancevic, J., & Konopaske, R. (2012). *Organizations: Behavior, Structure, Processes* (14th ed.). New York: Mc Graw Hill.
- [13.] Hackman, J. R., & Oldham, G. R. (1980). *Work Redesign*. United States: Addison-Wesley.
- [14.] Harter, J. K., Schmidt, F. L., & Hayes, T. L. (2002). Business-Unit-Level Relationship Between Employee Satisfaction, Employee Engagement, and Business Outcomes: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(2), 268-279. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.87.2.268>
- [15.] Hendrawan, A., Suchayawati, H., & Indriyani. (2017). Organizational Citizenship Behavior(OCB) Pada Karyawan Akademi Maritim Nusantara. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional & Internasional*, 39-48. Semarang: LPPM Universitas Muhammadiyah Semarang.
- [16.] Herminingsih, A. (2012). Spirituality and Job Satisfaction as Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). *Jurnal Ilmu Ekonomi Dan Sosial*, 1(2), 126-140.
- [17.] Huang, J., Wang, L., & Xie, J. (2014). Leader-Member Exchange and Organizational Citizenship Behavior: the Roles of Identification with Leader and Leader's Reputation. *Social Behavior and Personality An International Journal*, 42(10), 1699-1712. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2224/sbp.2014.42.10.1699>
- [18.] Humphrey, S. E., Nahrgang, J. D., & Morgeson, F. P. (2007). Integrating Motivational, Social, and Contextual Work Design Features: A Meta-Analytic Summary and Theoretical Extension of the Work Design Literature. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(5), 1332-1356. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.5.1332>
- [19.] Idowu, A. O. (2017). Effectiveness of Performance Appraisal System and its Effect on Employee Motivation. *Nile Journal of Business and Economics*, 5, 15-39.
- [20.] Ikhsan, M., Adam, M., & Faisal. (2019). The Effect of Transformational Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction and Employee's Performance of Aceh Education Agency. *The International Journal of Business Management and Technology*, 3(4), 1-8.
- [21.] Irwan, Musnadi, S., & Putra, T. R. I. (2021). Exploration The Impact Of The Conversion Process Of Bri To Bri Syariah On The Effect Of Compensation On Job Satisfaction And Work Motivation And Its Impact On Employee Performance Of Biregional Office Of Banda Aceh. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 4(1), 87-106. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.35409/IJBMER.2021.3232>
- [22.] Jannati, Lubis, A. R., & Putra, T. R. I. (2022). The Effect of Transformation Leadership Style and Compensation on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and Their Implications on the Performance of Police Apparatus at the Ditreskrim Polda Aceh. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 5(3), 146-164.

- <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.37502/IJSMR.2022.5313>
- [23.] Judge, T. A., & Mueller, J. D. K. (2012). Job Attitudes. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 63, 341–367. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-120710-100511>
- [24.] Khaidir, Yunus, M., & Idris, S. (2020). The Influence Of Sense Of Meaningfulness And Sense Of Trust On Organizational Citizenship Behavior And Its Implications On Performance Of Employee: Study In Bp2ip Malahayati Aceh. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Review*, 3(4), 72–83. <https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.35409/IJBMER.2020.3187>
- [25.] Kurniawan, F., Mukhlis, & Musnadi, S. (2020). The Effect of Work Environment and Service Facilities in Polres Pidie towards OCB Members with Work Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable. *International Journal of Research in Business and Technology*, 12(1), 149–156. Retrieved from <https://journals.techmindresearch.com/index.php/ijrbt>
- [26.] Lam, C. F., Wan, W., & Roussin, C. (2015). Going the Extra Mile and Feeling Energized: An Enrichment Perspective of Organizational Citizenship Behaviors. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 101(3). <https://doi.org/10.1037/apl0000071>
- [27.] Locke, E. A. (1976). *The Nature and Causes of Job Satisfaction*". *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. Chicago: Rand McNally.
- [28.] Mathis, J. (2006). *Human Resource Management* (10th ed.). Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [29.] Montani, F., Boudrias, J.-S., & Pigeon, M. (2017). Employee recognition, meaningfulness and behavioural involvement: test of a moderated mediation model. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(3), 356–384. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1288153>
- [30.] Muhammad, M., Musnadi, S., & Darsono, N. (2018). The Effect of Work Satisfaction and Downward Communication on Performance of West Aceh POLRES With Intrinsic Motivation as a Mediation Variable. *Proceeding of the First International Graduate Conference (IGC) On Innovation, Creativity, Digital, & Technopreneurship for Sustainable Development in Conjunction with The 6th Roundtable for Indonesian Entrepreneurship Educators 2018 Universitas Syiah Kua*. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.3-10-2018.2284288>
- [31.] Mukhlis, Musnadi, S., & Ridwan, N. (2020). The Effect of Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance and its Implication on the Performance of PT. PLN (Persero) Banda Aceh. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 3(3), 23–34.
- [32.] Munandar, A., Musnadi, S., & Sulaiman, S. (2019). The Effect of Work Stress, Work Load and Work Environment on Job Satisfaction And It's Implication on The Employee Performance of Aceh Investment And One Stop Services Agency. *International Graduate Conference (IGC)*, (Oktober). <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.3-10-2018.2284357>
- [33.] Munandar, A. S. (2001). *Industrial And Organizational Psychology*. Jakarta: Universitas Indonesia.
- [34.] Nasurdin, A. M., Nejati, M., & Mei, Y. K. (2013). Workplace spirituality and organizational citizenship behaviour: Exploring gender as a moderator. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 44(1), 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajbm.v44i1.148>
- [35.] Organ, D. W. (2015). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (Second). Amsterdam: Elsevier Ltd.
- [36.] Prawirosentono, S. (2010). *Human Resource Management: Employee Performance Policy: Tips for Building a Competitive Organization in the Free Trade Era of Dudia*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- [37.] Putri, A. R. (2018, January 13). Pentingnya "Organizational Citizenship Behavior" dalam Organisasi. *Kompasiana.Com*. Retrieved from <https://www.kompasiana.com/alifahputri/5a58faf2cf01b431412aee42/pentingnya-organizational-citizenship-behavior-dalam-organisasi?page=1>
- [38.] Ritonga, M. W. A. N., Ibrahim, M., & Bahri, S. (2019). The Practice of Work Culture, Suitability of Tasks, Leadership Style That has an Impact on Performance: The Role of Job Satisfaction as Mediating. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 8(4), 2147–4478.
- [39.] Rivai, V., & Sagala, E. J. (2014). *Human Resource Management for Companies: From Theory to Practice* (3rd ed.). Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- [40.] Robbins, S. P., & Judge, T. A. (2014). *Book Organizational Behavior Book 2 (1st Edition; translation D. Angelica, Ed.)*. Salemba Empat.
- [41.] Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-Determination Theory and the Facilitation of Intrinsic Motivation, Social Development, and Well-Being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1037110003-066X.55.1.68>
- [42.] Samsuar, Azis, N., & Faisal. (2019). The Influence of Organizational Commitment, Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance and its Implications on Performance of Operational Center Office at PT. Bank Aceh Syariah, Banda Aceh, Indonesia. *International Journal of Social Science & Economic Research*, 4(6), 4472–4486.
- [43.] Steger, M. F. (2012). Making Meaning in Life. *Psychological Inquiry*, 23, 381–385. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1047840X.2012.720832>

- [44.] Steger, M. F., & Dik, B. J. (2009). If One is Looking for Meaning in Life, Does it Help to Find Meaning in Work? *Applied Psychology: Health And Well-Being*, 1(3), 303–320. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1758-0854.2009.01018.x>
- [45.] Sudaryo, Y., & Sjarif, D. (2017). *Keuangan di Era Otonomi Daerah* (N. A. Sofiati & P. Christian, Eds.). Yogyakarta: Andi Publisher.
- [46.] Susanto, D. B., Faisal, & Putra, T. R. I. (2019). The Effect Of Knowledge Management, Organizational Learning And Work Satisfaction Toward Organizational Commitment And Its Impact On Employee Performance In Secretariat Office, District Of Nagan Raya, Aceh Province, Indonesia. *International Journal of Social Science and Economic Research*, (7), 5066–5076.
- [47.] Varihanna, Harmen, H., & Nizam, A. (2020). Effects of Organizational Trust and Justice on Job Satisfaction and their Consequences on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 3(4), 389–395. <https://doi.org/10.36349/EASJEBM.2020.v03i04.016>
- [48.] Yukl, G. (2010). Leadership in Organizations. In *The British Journal of Psychiatry* (Seventh Ed, Vol. 112). <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.112.483.211-a>